

CAUSES OF ZONOTIC INFECTIOUS DISEASES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7812653>

Abstract: In medicine, zoonotic infections are fundamentally different from other infections due to their extreme infectivity and high mortality rate. Every doctor should know the epidemiology, pathogenesis, clinical symptoms, diagnosis and prevention of these diseases. If the general and special measures taken in case of these diseases are not carried out in time, if the doctors are not able to choose the material from the patient for examination correctly, this disease can spread widely and escalate among the population.

Key words: brucellosis, yersinia, plague, tryptose-serum agar, glycerol, blood agar, orchitis, epididymitis,

Brucellosis (black lameness) is a widespread zoonotic disease, mainly affecting animals. The disease often occurs only in people who come into contact with animals. In this respect, brucellosis is an occupational disease. Brucellosis is caused by microorganisms belonging to the genus *Brucella*.

Morphology. *Brucella* are small, rod-shaped, 0.6–2.5 µm long, egg-shaped, cocci-shaped, 0.6–1.5 µm in diameter, and are located individually, in pairs or in groups. *Brucella*, the causative agent of disease in sheep and cattle, is mainly cocci-shaped, and in pigs, it has a rod-like shape. Brucellosis causative agents are polymorphic, so their morphology changes under the influence of physical, chemical and biological factors.

Brucella are sporeless, hyphal, and therefore do not form an immobile capsule, but some strains have a thin capsule under certain conditions. They are well dyed with all aniline dyes. Gram's stain is negative.

Growth. Brucella are strictly aerobic. It grows very slowly (in 3-10 days, in some cases in 15 days, mostly in 30 days). At a temperature of 37°C and a Pn of 6.8–7.4, as well as in normal nutrient media supplemented with vitamins, liver agar and broth, whey-glucose agar, whey potato water agar, blood agar, tryptose - Whey agar grows well in media supplemented with 5% glycerol. In liver agar, round, colorless, smooth, curved, S-shaped colonies are formed, and in liver broth, they form uniform clots and precipitates. They can also be grown in the yolk sac of a 10-12-day-old chicken embryo.

The first generation of *Br. abortus* grows well in 5–10% SO₂ as it acts as a growth factor. Certain dyes, antibiotics, including polymyxin-V, are added to the selective nutrient medium to isolate a pure culture of Brucella.

Pathogenicity to animals. Brucellosis infects sheep, goats, cattle, pigs, reindeer, llamas, horses and dogs, as well as a number of rodents (rats, mice, etc.). It can infect more than 60 species of vertebrates. A sick estuarine animal will give birth to a baby or give birth to a dead baby.

Animal waste (urine, feces, fetal fluid, vaginal secretions), especially milk products of goats and sheep, are highly contagious. A guinea pig is a very convenient experimental animal, when infected with Brucella, they are sick for 3 months and die from severe injuries to the bones, joints, ankles and eyes.

Pathogenesis of the disease in humans. Brucellosis infects people when they eat raw milk and dairy products (cheese, butter, cottage cheese, brinza), as well as undercooked or undercooked meat, or when they are in direct contact with them. The microbe enters the body through alimentary, contact and airborne routes. Since this is an occupational disease, it mainly affects veterinarians, zootechnicians, shepherds, employees of milk and cattle farms, poultry farms, cheese factories, as well as wool and skin receivers.

Brucellosis depends on the season, and in rural areas, it occurs mainly in the lambing period, that is, in March and May. In urban conditions, it can be found throughout the year.

The latent period of the disease can be 1-3 weeks, sometimes several months. Entering the body, Brucella settles in the lymph nodes, reticulo-endothelial system, where it multiplies and passes through the lymphatic channels into the blood, as a result of which a long-lasting bacteremia is observed. Through the blood, brucelli multiply in the spleen, spleen, and lymph nodes.

Humans and animals develop a slowly developing hypersensitivity, that is, an allergic state, from the first days of the disease, which persists during the disease and for a long time after the patient recovers.

Brucellosis is an acute septic and chronic disease, often chronic in humans with various clinical symptoms.

In the initial period of the disease, the patient's temperature rises gradually, reaches 40°C in 1-2 weeks, then begins to decrease, and returns again after 4-14 days. This situation can be repeated several times. When a fever breaks out, the patient's body trembles, his medicine dries up, when the fever subsides, he sweats profusely, and various rashes appear on his body. When brucellosis becomes chronic, gonads are damaged, as a result, orchitis, epididymitis, and in women, oophoritis and mastitis may develop. In some cases, infertility and miscarriages are observed in men and women as a result of infection.

Because *Brucella* lives inside the cell, the drug does not blind, they periodically multiply and enter the blood again, the disease renews, therefore, brucellosis lasts a long time and gives restitives (recurrence).

Mild, asymptomatic forms of the disease are somewhat difficult to detect, so this infection is diagnosed only with the help of laboratory tests.

Many clinical symptoms of brucellosis in humans are similar to those of malaria, tuberculosis, rheumatism, typhoid and typhoid fever, Ku-fever, so differential diagnosis is important.

The causative agent of the plague belongs to the genus *Yersinia*, the family of enterobacteria. It has an egg-shaped appearance and is bipolar. This infection is a zoonotic infection that mainly infects rodents and infects humans. Skin, lung, and intestinal forms are also found in plague.

Morphology. Plague bacterium is short, egg-shaped, oval, one side is more blunt, 1-2 µm long, 0.3-0.6 µm wide. *Touacteria* does not form inactive spores, but has a capsule. It is well stained with aniline dyes, in which the two ends are clear (bipolar staining), and the middle part of the body is colorless. Because there is more protoplasm at both ends of the microbe, and less in the middle of the body. grammanfie. Tone bacteria are variable, i.e. polymorphism. Therefore, if smears prepared from young cultures have an egg-shaped shape, when grown in solid or dense nutrient media, bacteria can be elongated, sometimes filamentous. L-shaped ones are also found among them.

Growth. Thon's pathogen is a facultative anaerobe, grows well in normal nutrient media with Pn 6.9–7.0. Growth is observed for three days, the optimum temperature is 28–30°C, but at 37°C it forms a capsule in selective media. Y.

restis can grow even at 450 C, if sodium sulfate or hemolyzed blood is added to the medium, the growth is accelerated.

When grown on meat-peptone agar, it forms small clear colonies. Later, the center of the colonies begins to darken, when you observe them, you can see young colonies that look like pieces of "broken glass". The edges of the colonies gradually bulge out, reminiscent of a "woven handkerchief". When it grows in the broth, it grows on its surface and forms a pilon, threads can hang from the pilon in the form of a stalactite. The Toun bacterium mainly forms virulent R-form colonies, sometimes S-forms are also found, but they are less virulent. In most cases, virulent colonies produce a dark pigment.

Pathogenicity to animals. Black and gray rats, mice, voles, gerbils, etc. are highly susceptible to the causative agent of toon. More than 300 species of rodents are known to be susceptible to toun, so rodents are the main hosts of this infection. Epizotia is observed between them.

Pathogenesis of the disease in humans. Tonsillitis bacteria are carried by rodents, so this disease is a zoonotic, naturally occurring infection. When the disease spreads among rodents, it also infects camels, cats, foxes and other animals. Humans are infected by transmissible, contact, air-dust, air-drop and alimentary ways. The cutaneous form of the disease develops when the causative agent of tonsillitis enters through injured skin (when bitten by a flea, when handling the skin of rodents). In the form of lungs, the bacteria enter through the air-droplet route, when talking to the patient or when he coughs with sputum. In enterprises receiving and processing leather, wool, the causative agent can also enter through dust in the air. The intestinal form of the disease occurs when the meat of a sick animal (camel) is eaten. If the microbe gets into the blood, the sepsis form of the disease develops. The latent period of the disease consists of 3-6 days, in some cases several hours. Cutaneous, bubonic, primary septic, secondary septic, primary and secondary pulmonary forms of tonsillitis differ depending on the location of the causative agent, the reactivity of the microorganism, the virulence of the bacterium, and the state of cellular and humoral immunity in a person.

A pustule and a carbuncle appear at the site of the pathogen in the skin form of toun. Often, there is no change here, the bacteria go through the lymphatic vessels to the nearby (regional) lymph nodes, where the inflammatory process begins, and as a result, the primary bubonic form appears; if the microbes get into the blood and damage other lymph nodes, secondary buboes are formed. In the septic form, the bacterium of tone is released into the external environment

with urine, feces, and sputum. In the primary pulmonary form, the bacteria enter through air droplets, if it passes through the blood, then the secondary pulmonary form develops. In the form of lungs, the microbe is mainly excreted with sputum.

Ton's disease begins suddenly: the patient shakes violently, has a headache, the face turns pale and blue, it looks like the face of a person who is afraid (facies pestica), these symptoms apply to all stages of toun's disease. Each form has its own clinical symptoms. Before the discovery of antibiotics, the death rate from tonsillitis was very high (40–90%). Due to the large number of desert zones in our republic, there is a risk of taun disease appearing among animals and sometimes also among people.

Treatment and prevention. Down's disease is treated comprehensively. Patients are given streptomycin. It gives good results in all forms of the disease. If chloramphenicol or tetrastictin is given together with streptomycin, the result is even better. In addition to these, gammaglobulin and special bacteriophage are also used against tonsillitis.

Use of dry, live EV vaccine for special prevention. In 1926, Girard and Rabik isolated the EV strain from the body of a child who died of typhus on the island of Madagascar, grew it in GPA for 5 years, reduced its virulence, and managed to create a vaccine strain that preserved its immunological properties.

The vaccine is injected subcutaneously, between the skin, and on the skin 1-2 times. The resulting immunity protects for up to one year. Currently, there is no compulsory vaccination against typhus. Because in many countries this infection has decreased due to the general vaccination of the population.

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